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47. A Study on Customer Awareness towards Green Banking- with Special reference to Tirunelveli District

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ABSTRACT

In the present era the ecological preservation and development are recognized globally for protecting our earth from global warming and climatic change. Due to this there is a wave of changes with all business activities and they started to focus on people and planet and not on their profit alone. This leads to a move towards green economy and one such area is green banking. Green banking is comparatively a new development in this modern world. It is a form of banking taking into account the social and environmental impact. Its main motive is to protect and preserve environment. The banking sector should go green and also should play a pro-active role to take environmental and ecological aspects as a part of their lending principle. This paper attempts to find out the major problems in creating awareness among customers about green banking in tirunelveli district. This study also focuses on the effect of demonetization in the usage of green banking system. The researcher collects primary data through questionnaire from 150 respondents. The collected data are analyzed using percentage technique and Garrett ranking method. The secondary data are collected from various bank websites, RBI reports, journals etc. The findings of the study are that the banks have to take green initiatives in a big way and also should create a awareness among customers about green banking.

Key words: Green banking strategies, products, initiative, customer awareness.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of Green Banking is emerged in 2009. Green Banking is not a separate bank. Green Banking means ensuring environment friendly practices in banking sector and thereby reducing internal and external carbon footprints. Banking industry is generally not considered as polluting industry. But it impacts the environment in terms of increasing energy consumption (lighting, air conditioning), paper consumption. Green banking considers all the social and environmental/ecological factors with an aim to protect the environment and conserve natural resources. It is also called as an ethical bank or a sustainable bank. Green Banking therefore covers two aspects. The first one being judicious use of all resources, energy and reducing carbon footprints and second being encouraging and financing only environment friendly investment. So Green Banking is not only about making sustainable use of resources but also about environment friendly. The Institute for Development and Research in Banking and Technology established by RBI defines Green Banking as:

'Green Banking is an umbrella term referring to practices and guidelines that make banks sustainable in economic, environment, and social dimensions. It aims to make banking processes and the use of IT and physical infrastructure as efficient and effective as possible, with zero or minimal impact on the environment.'

1.1 IMPORTANCE OF GREEN BANKING

The importance of Green Banking in India is increasing rapidly as it is moving on the path of economic development and industrial sector is playing an important role in that. However, Indian industry faces the challenges of controlling environmental impact of their business i.e. reducing pollution and emission of their clients. Though government has been trying to address the issue by framing environmental legislations and encouraging industry to follow

environmental technologies and practices, they would not be enough given the poor track records of enforcement, public awareness and inability to derive competitive advantage by producing eco-friendly products. As Banking sector is one of the major source of financing to the industries thus the banking operation and investment by financial institutions should take care of environmental management of these polluting industries by improving the overall environment, the quality and conservation of life, level of efficiency in using materials and energy, quality of services and products.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Bahl (2012) highlights the means of creating awareness about Green Banking to ensure sustainable growth. Garrett's ranking technique is used to analyze the most significant strategies in respect of Green Banking.

Jha&Bhame (2013) found the ways to Go Green through "Green Banking". The research methodology used in this study is based on primary as well as secondary data. The primary data was collected from the study conducted through telephonic interactions and personal interviews. The study examines major aspects concerned with the Green Banking. Specially structured questionnaires and interviews with employees, of well established banks and general public have been used for survey purpose.

Rajesh &Dileep (2014) studied the role of banks in sustainable economic development through Green Banking activities. The study was based on secondary data obtained from the reports of various Banks, various seminars and workshop information and other relative information published on the banks and other internet sites. The study concluded that Banks also contribute to ecological footprint directly and indirectly through investment/lending in their customer enterprises.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To understand the concept and importance of 'Green Banking'

To identify the products of Green Banking.

To create awareness about green banking among the general public and customers.

To find out the challenges in implementation of green banking in India.

To analyse whether demonetization has increased the usage of green banking system among the customers.

4. RESEARCH DESIGN

This study is a descriptive survey study. Primary data is collected through self structured questionnaire. Secondary data is collected from existing reports, books, journals & magazines and websites. The sample size of the study was 150 respondents and they were selected from Tirunelveli at random according to the convenience. Statistical tools like percentage analysis, likert scale methods, Garrett Ranking method were used.

5. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

Table 5.1: Demographic Profile

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Up to 25 years	76	51%
	25 to 35 years	31	21%
	35 to 45 years	27	18%
	Above 45 years	16	10%

Gender	Male	95	63%
	Female	55	37%
Marital status	Married	89	59%
	unmarried	61	41%
Place	Rural	93	62%
	Urban	57	38%
Educational qualification	12th	20	13%
	UG	86	57%
	PG	28	19%
	others	16	11%
Income per month	Up to Rs 10000	55	37%
	Rs 10000 to Rs 20000	63	42%
	Rs 20000 to Rs 30000	28	19%
	More than Rs 30000	4	2%
Type of bank	Public sector bank	93	62%
	Private sector bank	45	30%
	Foreign bank	12	8%
Size of the bank	Small size	25	17%
	Medium size	91	61%
	Large size	34	23%
Green banking services	Vital	20	13%
	Essential	80	53%
	Desirable	35	23%
	Cannot say exactly	15	10%
Information about green banking services	Bank officials	20	13%
	Advertisement	18	12%
	Tv& radio	90	60%
	Friends & Family	22	15%
Green banking cheaper than traditional banking	Yes	105	70%
	No	45	30%
Link between green banking & demonetization	Yes	100	67%
	No	50	33%
Whether the demonetization has increased the usage of green banking system	Yes	95	63%
	No	55	37%

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

From the above table 5.1 it is inferred that Majority of the respondents are bellow 25 years of age. Majority of the respondents are male. Majority of the respondents are married. Majority of the respondents reside in rural area. Majority of the respondents have completed their UG degree. Majority of the respondents have a monthly income of Rs 10000 to Rs 20000.

Majority of the respondents have account in public sector banks. Majority of the respondents have account in medium size bank. Majority of the respondents say that green banking service is essential. Majority of the respondents say that they get information about green banking from T.V & Radio. Majority of the respondents say that green banking is cheaper than traditional banking. Majority of the respondents feel that there is link between green banking and demonetization. Majority of the respondents say that the demonetization has increased the usage of green banking system.

Table: 5.2 Awareness of customers about green banking products

S.No	particulars	aware		Not aware	
		No of respondents	percentage	No of respondents	percentage
1	Green banking	130	87%	20	13%
2	Green loan	44	29%	106	71%
3	Green mortgages	70	47%	80	53%
4	Online bill payment	94	62%	56	37%
5	Cash deposit system	85	57%	65	53%

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

From the above table 5.2 it is inferred that

- Majority of the respondents are aware of green banking.
- Majority of the respondents are not aware of green loan.
- Majority of the respondents are not aware of green mortgage.
- Majority of the respondents are aware of online bill payment.
- Majority of the respondents are aware of cash deposit system.

Table: 5.3 Methods of creating awareness

Ranking method is used to analyze the methods of creating awareness about green banking among the respondents.

S.no	Factors	Weighted score	average score	Rank
1	Make them cheaper by reducing charges / fees	598	119.6	I
2	Incentives to green banking users	594	118.8	II
3	Advertisement	494	98.8	IV
4	Contacting every customer personally	556	111.2	III
5	Giving them guarantee of data security and privacy	450	90	V

Source : Data collected through questionnaire

The above table 5.3 shows that majority of our respondents feel that awareness about green banking can be created by making them cheaper followed by giving incentives to green banking users and by contacting every customer personally.

Table 5.4 Challenges faced by customer in adopting green banking system

Factors	I (80)	II (69)	III (59)	IV (53)	V (47)	VI (40)	VII (32)	VIII (20)	Score	Avg. Score	Rank
1. Lack of education	40 3200	34 2346	28 1652	16 848	12 564	10 400	08 256	02 40	9306	62.04	I
2. Technical issues	36 2880	30 2070	24 1416	12 636	16 752	14 560	12 384	06 120	8818	58.79	III
3. Traditional approach	38 3040	32 2208	26 1534	14 742	14 658	12 480	10 320	04 80	9062	60.41	II
4. Lack of infrastructure	34 2720	28 1932	22 1298	10 530	18 846	16 640	14 448	08 160	8574	57.16	IV
5. Lack of knowledge of technology	28 2240	22 1518	16 944	04 212	24 1128	22 880	20 640	14 280	7842	52.28	VII
6. Lack of confidence	32 2560	26 1794	20 1180	08 424	20 940	18 720	16 512	10 200	8330	55.53	V
7. No direct interaction with the banker	30 2400	24 1656	18 1062	06 318	22 1034	20 800	18 576	12 240	8086	53.91	VI

Source : Data collected through questionnaire

The above table 5.4 shows that majority of our respondents face the challenges of lack of education followed by the impact of traditional approach and followed by technical issues in adopting the greener banking.

6. CONCLUSION

Banks are responsible corporate citizens. Banks believe that every small 'GREEN' step taken today would go a long way in building a greener future and that each one of them can work towards to better global environment. Basically green banking avoids as much as paper work, you get go green credit cards, go green mortgages and also all the transactions done through online Banking. It Create awareness to business people about environmental and social responsibility enabling them to do an environmental friendly business practice.

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